

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D2.1 – Report on key-parameters and predictive models of degradation– v1.2

Deliverable information

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Spoke Partners

No.	Name of Partner	Acronym	Role
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2	University of Bologna	UNIBO	Member
2	University of Napoli Federico II	UNINA	Member
4	Sapienza University of Rome	UNIROMA1	Member
5	University of Catania	UNICT	Affiliated by "Convenzione"
6	Opificio delle Pietre Dure	OPD	Spoke co-leader

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to define key parameters and develop predictive models for the degradation processes of selected cultural heritage materials, namely: a selection of pigments and binding media, natural and artificial stones, metals, and paper.

The research activity integrated existing and new knowledge derived from the study of specific historical objects exhibiting degradation issues with that obtained from laboratory-prepared mock-ups. These mock-ups were subjected to accelerated artificial aging treatments under controlled exposure to light, humidity, temperature, and environmental pollutants (e.g., saline solutions and sulfur-containing gases). The effects of various microbiological species (bacteria and fungi) on paper-based materials were also investigated.

For each class of analyzed materials, the effects of the aforementioned physical, chemical, and microbiological parameters were successfully evaluated using a wide range of state-of-the-art analytical methods, operating from the macro to the nanoscale. Experimental results obtained from selected pigments and stones were collected and used to develop and optimize mathematical models aimed at predicting their overall degradation processes over time. A detailed description of the analytical approaches employed for material characterization is provided in deliverable 2.2.

This research activity results from collaborative efforts within the Consortium, involving research institutions, including CNR (SCITEC, ISPC, IAC) and the Opificio delle Pietre Dure, and academic institutions (UNIBO, UNICT, UNINA, UNIROMA1), as well as several European research infrastructure facilities, such

as the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) and various large-scale facilities (e.g., the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility – ESRF – in Grenoble, France).

Despite the ongoing collection and processing of some data, the outcomes achieved so far, as described in the present deliverable, are expected to establish a solid scientific predictive basis for breakthrough perspectives in the preventive conservation of historical objects in museums and heritage sites. These outcomes will also form the basis for the finalization of deliverable 2.3, *"Report on Monitoring Strategies and Preventive Conservation Guidelines for Heritage Objects at Degradation Risk."*

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1. Introduction

This document describes the outcomes of the research activity carried out by the Consortium in Spoke 5, Work Package 2, on key parameters and predictive models for the degradation processes of selected cultural heritage materials (deliverable 2.1).

Section 2 (Experimental results) presents state-of-the-art and key-degradation parameters of the materials chosen for this research activity, namely: selected classes of copper-, sulfide-, lead-, and cobalt-based pigments, and oily and proteinaceous binders (par. 2.1); natural and artificial stones (par. 2.2); metals (par. 2.3); paper-based materials (par.2.4). The results presented in this section are derived from the experimental approaches described in detail in deliverable 2.2.

Section 3 (Predictive models for degradation) details the mathematical predictive model for the light-induced degradation of pigments, with a specific application to cadmium yellows.

Section 4 reports the concluding remarks of the research activities, including their interconnections with the activities currently being developed within Spoke 5, Work Package 1, *“Advanced Non-Invasive Methods for Sustainable Diagnostics in Heritage Science,”* and future collaborative exchanges with the PNRR H2IOSC project, the *“Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud.”* (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>).

The outreaches of this deliverable, including publications and participation in conferences and workshops, are listed in deliverable 2.2, *“Technical report on*

the diagnostic methods applied to the chemical and microbiological degradation of different heritage materials”.

2. Experimental results

2.1 Paintings

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2.1.1 State of the art

The final appearance of a painting is the result of the complex interaction between the materials used as pigments, responsible for the color of the paint layer, and organic binders, which define the painting technique. However, paintings are not stable or immovable, and reactions take place over time, which strongly influence their final visual aspect. Once applied, the paint undergoes chemical reactions, resulting in the formation of a dry film. Further chemical changes occur during aging, such as oxidation and cross-linking of the organic media, reactions between the paint binder and the pigments, as well as the pigments' interaction with the atmosphere [1,2]. It has been extensively documented that amorphous or crystalline carboxylates of metal ions (soaps) [3] and newly formed compounds arising from changes in the oxidation state of one or more elements constituting some inorganic or organo-metal pigments [4,5] are common alteration products of paint components.

Chemical alteration of copper-based blue and green pigments (synthetic or mineral), such as copper carbonates and copper arsenites, has been observed to cause color change due to external factors, such as exposure to sulfurous and

chlorinated pollutants, moisture, high temperatures, and both alkaline and acidic conditions [6–8]. The presence of other paint components, like sulfide-containing pigments, can also play a role. For example, alkaline environments and high temperatures can promote the formation of tenorite (CuO), while chlorides—whether from external sources or inherent in the material—can induce corrosion phenomena [6].

Different types of metal arsenates, often identified with copper (II) soaps, have been hypothesized as alteration products of the emerald green pigment $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 3\text{Cu}(\text{AsO}_2)_2]$ in discolored 19th century oil paintings due to moisture and the acidity of the paint [7,8].

Orpiment ($\alpha\text{-As}_2\text{S}_3$), and realgar (As_4S_4), among other arsenic-containing pigments, are known to undergo discoloration upon exposure to visible light [9–13]. The red-orange realgar undergoes photo-induced degradation, becoming friable and transforming to yellow para-realgar (a polymorph of realgar) and/or colorless arsenolite (As_2O_3). In contrast, orpiment photo-oxidizes primarily to arsenolite [9]. Besides light, other factors have been reported to prompt the degradation of this pigment to arsenic (III) and/or arsenic (V) compounds, including humidity, local acidity of the paint, nature of the binding medium, and pigments and/or metals mixed into the paint [9,11,14,15].

Other sulfide pigments susceptible to discoloration include cadmium yellows ($\text{CdS}/\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$) [16–19] and red vermilion (known as the mineral cinnabar; $\alpha\text{-HgS}$) [20]. The photo-oxidation of cadmium yellow to cadmium sulfate in oil paints has been attributed to the combined action of moisture and either light or chloride species [16,17,19]. In tempera and oil paints, the oxidation of HgS to

mercury sulfate and chloride, followed by reduction to Hg(0), is attributed to light and chlorine-containing compounds [20–23].

Red lead (called “minium” in its mineral form; Pb_3O_4) is known for its photocatalytic properties in oil paintings. Its conduction band can reduce Pb^{4+} to Pb^{2+} and simultaneously induces the decarboxylation of the oil binder at the pigment surface, releasing CO_2 that reacts with Pb^{2+} to form various white lead carbonates [24,25]. The blackening of this pigment and that of lead white is a widespread phenomenon observed in mural paintings. It can result from the interaction of the paint with environmental factors, such as different gaseous pollutants, humidity, temperature, specific oxidizing agents (e.g., hypochlorous acid), microbial activity and intrinsic factor of the paint (e.g., pH). More specifically, red lead darkens, forming plattnerite in acidic conditions, or whitens as lead carbonates into cerussite ($PbCO_3$) and hydrocerussite ($Pb_3(CO_3)_2(OH)_2$). In neutral to alkaline conditions, chlorine can cause the oxidation of lead carbonates into plattnerite (β - PbO_2) or scrutinyite (α - PbO_2) [26–28]. Moreover, lead soaps can form, affecting both its appearance and its structural integrity [29].

Soaps of potassium have been observed among the degradation compounds of discolored smalt, a blue cobalt-containing glass of variable composition, widely used as a blue pigment in oil paintings from the mid-15th century [30,31]. These compounds form from the interaction between potassium leached from the silicate network and fatty acids in the oily binder, concurrent with the transition of cobalt ions from tetrahedral (blue) to octahedral (pinkish) coordination geometry [32,33]. The overall degradation pathways are influenced by moisture

and temperature as well as various internal factors, such as grain size and chemical composition of the pigment, nature of the binder (i.e., lime, oil, tempera), and local pH of the paint [32–35].

With respect to the copper-, sulfide-, lead-, and cobalt-based pigments mentioned above, a systematic study aimed at exploring the effects of various environmental factors, such as humidity, temperature, light, and pollutants, as well as different organic binders, on the overall alteration processes has not yet been performed.

Regarding the binding medium, although modifications arising from binders-pigments interactions may change drastically the appearance and physico-chemical stability of a painting, very little has been published about these changes and research has mainly focused on oily media. In particular, very little is known about the nature of the interactions between the inorganic pigments and the proteinaceous binders, and their impact on paint aging under variable environmental conditions [36].

In the following paragraphs, the results from paint mock-ups before and after different aging protocols (see deliverable 2.2 for further details), with systematic variations in pH, temperature, relative humidity (RH), light and/or saline exposure, will be described.

2.1.2 Key-parameters of degradation of selected pigments

In Table 1, a summary of the results obtained from the multi-technique and multi-scale study of the paint mock-ups described in deliverable 2.2 is provided. Key degradation factors have already been identified for a selection of samples, while other analyses are still ongoing, and results will be provided upon

submission of an updated version of this deliverable. A selection of results obtained from the study of emerald green, and Scheele's green, cadmium sulfide and cerussite paint mock-ups is described in paragraphs 2.1.2.1-2.1.2.4.

Table 1. Summary of the analyzed mock-ups with corresponding key-degradation factors and the identified main alteration compounds.

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Paint mock-up	Key degradation factors	Main alteration compounds	Partners involved
Copper-based pigments			
Emerald green oil paint	UVA-VIS light RH≥95%	Arsenic (V) compounds As ₂ O ₃	CNR-SCITEC, UNIPG
	UVA-VIS light, RH≥95%	Arsenic (V) compounds, As ₂ O ₃ , Copper (II) soaps	
Scheele's green oil paint	UVA-VIS light RH≥95%	Arsenic (V) compounds As ₂ O ₃	CNR-SCITEC, UNIPG
	UVA-VIS light, RH≥95%	Arsenic (V) compounds, As ₂ O ₃ , Copper (I) compounds, possible organo-metal compound	
Egyptian Blue, Egyptian Green	T= 40°C, RH =94% Saline exposure	CuO, Cl ₂ corrosion	CNR-ISPC
Azurite, Malachite	T= 40°C, RH =94% Saline exposure	CuO, Cl ₂ corrosion	CNR-ISPC
Han Blue	T= 40°C, RH =94% Saline exposure	CuO, Cl ₂ corrosion	CNR-ISPC
Chrysocolla	T= 40°C, RH =94% Saline exposure	CuO, Cl ₂ corrosion	CNR-ISPC
Conichalcite, Copper resinate, Copper Blue, Dioptase	ongoing	ongoing	CNR-ISPC
Sulfide-based pigments			
Cadmium yellow oil paint	UVA-VIS light, RH≥95%	CdSO ₄	CNR-SCITEC, UNIPG
Orpiment oil/egg/gum arabic paints	Ongoing	Ongoing (see preliminary results – Fig. 3)	CNR-ISPC, CNR-SCITEC, UNIBO, UNIPG
Realgar oil/egg/gum arabic paints	ongoing	ongoing	CNR-ISPC, CNR-SCITEC, UNIBO, UNIPG
Red vermilion	UV-VIS light	ongoing	CNR-ISPC
Lead-based pigments			
Cerussite	T=25°C, RH=90%, pH=5	Plattnerite, lead sulfide, lead sulfates	CNR-ISPC
Hydrocerussite	T=25°C, RH=90%, pH=5	Plattnerite, lead sulfide, lead sulfates	CNR-ISPC
Red lead	ongoing	ongoing	CNR-ISPC
Cobalt-based pigments			
Smalt	T= 25°C, RH=90%, pH=9	Potassium Leaching, silica network etching, changes in cobalt coordination geometry	CNR-ISPC

2.1.2.1 Emerald green and Scheele's green. Emerald green and Scheele's green oil paint mock-ups were subjected to artificial aging to understand the effect of different environmental parameters, specifically light and humidity, on the degradation of these green pigments in the oily binder (see deliverable 2.2 for details).

Exposure to indoor lighting conditions has induced a small color modification (Fig. 1a), just above the threshold comparable or below the human eye ($\Delta E^*_{1976} \approx 1.5-3.5$) [37], calculated from the reflectance spectrum, which didn't show considerable changes because of photoaging (Fig. 1b). Overall, the slight color changes resulted from a decrease in luminosity, the green color fraction, and the yellow component (data not shown), thus resulting in a weak darkening and loss of glossiness. However, despite the slight visual modification, external reflection mode IR spectroscopy of photoaged samples (Fig. 1c) highlighted modifications to both arsenite and acetate moieties in the pigments' structures. Considering previous studies on the degradation of emerald green [7,8,38–42] and IR studies on arsenic compounds (arsenites/arsenates)[43,44] spectral changes observed in the $950-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range can be reasonably ascribed to the formation of arsenic (V) compounds. To prove the oxidation of arsenic, IR results were combined with those arising from SR μ -XRF and μ -XANES spectroscopy measurements at As K- (Fig. 1d-f) and Cu K-edges (data not shown) performed at the synchrotron radiation (SR) facility ESRF (Grenoble, FR). These measurements proved that the light exposure promoted the transformation of original As^{3+} -species [i.e., arsenite $(\text{As}_3\text{O}_6)^{3-}$] to As^{5+} -compounds, within the uppermost 5-8 μm of the stratigraphy, while Cu^{2+} -

species were not involved in redox reactions and preserved their original oxidation number. The amorphous nature of these photodegradation compounds was suggested by the absence of any crystalline As^{5+} -containing phase in the altered layer, as revealed by SR μ -XRD mapping. A similar behavior was observed for the photoaged Scheele's green paint mock-up, where surface-stratified arsenic oxidation was detected.

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Figure 1. a) Photographs of emerald green oil paint mock-up before (left) and after (right) exposure to UVA-VIS light at environmental humidity (approximately 35% RH) with corresponding color variation expressed as ΔE^*_{1976} . b) VIS reflectance spectra acquired on the paint mock-up before (black) and after (red) photoaging. c) Pseudo-absorbance IR spectra recorded from the surface of the mock-up before (unaged) and after (aged) exposure to UVA-VIS light. d) Photomicrograph of a thin-section obtained from the aged mock-up. e) RGB SR μ -XRF maps of $\text{As}^{3+}/\text{As}^{5+}/\text{Cu-K}$. f) Selection of As K-edge μ -XANES spectra (black) acquired from the surface and bulk of the thin-section shown in e).

Overall, a surface-stratified oxidative alteration of arsenite ions has been induced by light exposure, despite only slight changes in color and optical properties of the paint surface were observed (cf. Table 1 for results obtained

from further mock-ups aged in different conditions).

2.1.2.2 Cadmium yellow (hexagonal CdS). The degradation pathways of several oil paint mock-ups made of hexagonal CdS have been monitored at different stages of photoaging. The aging protocol has been conducted under controlled conditions of light (UVA-VIS) and moisture ($RH \geq 95\%$) (see deliverable 2.2 for details). Measurements are aimed at producing new datasets exploited for the development and optimization of a mathematical model to predict the degradation pathways of CdS in oil paintings (see [45] and Section 3 for details). Starting from previous knowledge [17,46,47], the monitoring of $CdSO_4$ formation and the changes in the oily binder was performed at increasing steps of radiant energy per area values, ranging from 2.5×10^4 $W \cdot h/m^2$ up to 7.1×10^5 $W \cdot h/m^2$ (Fig. 2a). Chromatic changes (expressed as ΔE^*_{1976}) and chemical changes of the paint surface were followed by a range of non-invasive spectroscopic techniques, namely: reflectance VIS spectroscopy, colorimetry and external reflection mode FT-IR spectroscopy.

Despite the minor changes detected in the reflectance VIS spectra and colorimetry ($\Delta E^*_{1976} < 5$) (Fig. 2b), reflection FT-IR data reveal clear signals indicating the progressive formation of $CdSO_4$ starting from the first stage of photoaging (Fig. 2c). The gradual formation of such compound is pointed out by the increasing of its characteristic IR band positioned around $1200\text{--}1000$ cm^{-1} [$\nu(SO_4^{2-})$ modes] and the signal at ca. 610 cm^{-1} [$\delta(SO_4^{2-})$] at increasing stages of photoaging.

Figure 2. a) Photographs of cadmium sulfide (CdS) oil paint mock-ups before (t0) and after exposure to UVA-VIS light and high humidity (RH ≥ 95%) at two different stages of photoaging. b) Reflectance VIS spectra and c) IR spectra acquired from paint mock-ups at increasing stages of photoaging. T0 spectra are shown in black/grey, while spectra acquired after photoaging are shown in colored lines. In c), dashed rectangles point out to the sulfate group vibrational modes.

The acquisition of images of each sample by a high-resolution microscope (Hirox) is still ongoing to identify changes in the surface morphology of each painting subjected to aging (data not shown). In parallel, further efforts are underway to determine the thickness of the sulfate-rich alteration layer using μ -FT-IR, μ -Raman and S K-edge μ -XANES spectroscopic techniques by analysis of paint thin sections.

2.1.2.3 Orpiment. To elucidate orpiment degradation pathways, paint mock-ups were subjected to controlled aging conditions (see deliverable 2.2 for details). Measurements are ongoing to identify degradation products and the factors driving these transformations. Preliminary findings are described below, particularly concerning the formation and detection of elemental sulfur in egg yolk and gum arabic paint mock-ups exposed to high humidity (94% RH) at 40°C

and in a basic environment (pH 9). This phenomenon has been rarely observed in Heritage Science; in fact, sulfur is typically found as sulfates or organosulfur compounds during orpiment degradation [11,14,15]. A recent mineralogical study [10] has deepened our understanding of sulfur release from crystalline orpiment, demonstrating that it is significantly influenced by elevated pH, increased levels of dissolved oxygen, and high temperature. In line with these findings, our experimental results (Fig. 3) revealed that a combination of alkaline pH, darkness, and high relative humidity led to a distinctive glittering effect on the samples. This effect was characterized by the formation of large arsenolite crystals on the surface along with sulfur-enriched macro-aggregations. It remains to be clarified whether the glittering effect is caused by the arsenolite crystals, the sulfur aggregates, or a combination of both. The same results were observed in the Book of dead of Kha, as detailed in deliverable 2.2.

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Figure 3. VIS image acquired using a Dino-Lite microscope of artificially aged As_2S_3 in arabic gum (RH%=94%, T=40°C, pH 9); Elemental distribution map acquired on the mock-up by μ -XRF imaging (lateral resolution 15 μ m).

2.1.2.4 Cerussite. Laboratory tests have been conducted to replicate lead-white oxidation processes and clarify their driving factors, which remain not completely understood [26–28]. To this purpose, both cerussite and hydrocerussite mock-ups were prepared. The effects of other pigments, including orpiment, on the darkening process was assessed in the egg binding

medium after exposure to high humidity, room temperature, and acidic pH conditions (Fig. 4, topmost photographs). In line with the literature, a severe darkening was observed on the treated mock-up. Within two weeks, cerussite transformed into a black phase identified as plattnerite through MA-XRD mapping analysis (Fig. 4, bottommost maps).

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Figure 4. VIS image acquired with Dino-Lite microscope of orpiment layer over cerussite ground in an egg tempera paint mock-up before (top-left) and after (top-right) aging ($T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=81\%$, $\text{pH}=5$). MA-XRD maps of crystalline orpiment, cerussite and plattnerite.

2.1.3 Key-parameters of degradation of proteinaceous binder

Innovative proteomics approaches based on nano-LC-MS/MS [48,49] were used to study the chemical modifications undergone by the proteins because of aging and depending on the pigment. Further details about the sample preparation and analysis are provided in deliverable 2.2. As an initial approach to this problem, we studied the interaction of casein (a proteinaceous binder used in the tempera technique) with four inorganic pigments commonly employed in paintings: azurite ($\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$), Saint John's white (CaCO_3), red vermilion (HgS) and red lead (Pb_3O_4). Paint mock-ups were prepared by applying pigments mixed with aqueous solutions/dispersions of casein onto glass slides. The

resulting paint films were artificially aged and then scratched to obtain fine powders.

Deamidation is a general and relevant process on the myriad changes that proteins undergo and is influenced by the age and more generally by the preservation state of the sample under consideration.

As expected, proteins in our samples are extensively deamidated (Fig. 5, upper panel). It is worth mentioning that the control sample (casein only) is less deamidated compared to the samples containing pigment. Furthermore, no significant differences are observed in the percentage values among the pigment-containing samples, suggesting that pigment does not significantly affect the extent of deamidation (Fig. 5, lower panel).

Figure 5. Overall percentage of deamidation for asparagine (N) and glutamine (Q) residues (upper panel), reported as percentage of modified over detected (modified plus unmodified) ones. Cumulative extent of deamidation (N,Q) (lower panel). Error bars represent standard deviation.

The extent of deamidation along the sequences of Alpha-S1 casein and Alpha-S2

casein was also evaluated, highlighting regions of the protein that are more modified compared to others, suggesting greater exposure in the protein's 3D structure or even involvement in interactions with pigments. Alpha-S1 casein showed that the same sites are always deamidated, regardless of the pigment, except for the region including sites 146-155 which is deamidated only in the case of carbonate as a pigment.

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When looking at modifications occurring on lysine side chain, such as carbamylation, carboxymethylation, formylation, aminoadipic acid formation and carboxyethylation, all termed as AGE modifications, the sample with carbonate as pigment is the most modified one.

Backbone cleavage of the polypeptide chain is also expected as a degradation feature in aged proteins and can be evaluated since, upon trypsin hydrolysis, semi-tryptic peptides are generated. The frequency of semitryptic peptides, based on spectrum matches, was evaluated as percentage of semitryptic peptides over the total number of identified peptides for each chain. The frequency of backbone cleavages is generally high. However, no clear-cut difference was observed among the samples or compared with the control sample.

2.2 Stones

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2.2.1 State of the art

Natural stone and artificial geomaterials undergo complex deterioration processes due to influences of water penetration, temperature variations, and pollutants [50–53]. These factors affect the mineralogical and chemical composition of the artifacts and modify physical and aesthetic characteristics [50,54]. This degradation puts at risk the durability and historical significance of cultural heritage [55].

The application of UNI standards in studying cultural geomaterials provides a reliable framework for evaluating their physical and mechanical properties, offering significant insights into their durability and conservation needs [56]. UNI EN 1925 outlines methods for determining the water absorption by capillarity, essential parameter for evaluating the material-environmental factor interaction [57,58]. Similarly, UNI EN 12370 provides a standardized approach for testing resistance to salt crystallization, a common mechanism of deterioration in cultural heritage materials exposed to saline environments [59]. By simulating the cyclic action of soluble salts crystallizing within the pores, this test identifies materials tendency to cracking and material loss under such conditions [60]. Its application is particularly relevant for artifacts located in coastal areas or environments with anthropogenic salt contamination. Together, these standards support a scientific and systematic approach to preserve the historical and cultural value of heritage materials [61,62].

2.2.2 Key-parameters of degradation

The study investigated the degradation of natural and artificial stone materials through a combination of controlled laboratory tests (see deliverable 2.2 for details). The tests focused on water absorption and salt crystallization, conducted following the UNI EN 1925 and UNI EN 12370 standards. The materials studied included experimental mortars and natural stones.

Several categories of innovative mortars were tested:

- Hydraulic mortars developed based on an ancient Roman recipe, in cubic samples with dimensions of $4 \times 4 \times 4 \text{ cm}^3$.
- Aerial mortars, simple and with the addition of organic additives extracted from microalgae and acrylic additives. These samples were approximately $4 \times 4 \times 2 \text{ cm}^3$.
- Lime mortars with two different volcanic aggregates (ghiara and azolo) typical of the Etna territory, in cubic specimens with dimensions $4 \times 4 \times 4 \text{ cm}^3$.

The study also included three types of natural stone:

- White Carrara marble in cubic samples, approximately $5 \times 5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^3$.
- Travertine, as 5 cm side cubes.
- Wakestone, in shape of cylindrical samples measuring 4 cm in diameter and 5 cm in height.

The water absorption tests followed UNI EN 1925, where dried samples were partially immersed in distilled water (depth of $3 \pm 1 \text{ mm}$). Periodic weighing allowed calculation of the absorption coefficient, which reflects how materials respond to moisture exposure.

The salt crystallization tests, conducted according to UNI EN 12370, evaluated

material resistance under cyclic exposure to saline solutions and drying. Samples were immersed in a 14% NaCl solution followed by cycles of drying at 105°C and cooling at room temperature. The process was repeated 15 times, with degradation monitored through visual inspections for cracks, weight loss, and material disintegration.

The analysis of weight variation over time during water absorption tests revealed distinct behaviors between the lithotypes and mortars. Natural stones reached a stable weight quickly, except for travertine, due to its porous nature. Hydraulic mortars absorb water gradually during the test, whereas aerial mortars gain weight rapidly first, and then regularly. In Figure 6, the capillary water absorption trends for all the natural samples are shown: travertine (T1-T6), wakestone (W1-W3), and marble (M1-M3). Travertine exhibits variable behavior depending on the orientation of anisotropy planes, with T1-T3 characterized by faster absorption rates compared to T4-T6. Wakestone and marble display more contained and stable curves over time.

Figure 6. Natural sample water absorption trends.

Figures 7 and 8, instead, illustrate the water absorption test results for samples of hydraulic mortars (Fig. 7) and aerial mortars (Fig. 8). It can be observed in both cases that the initial absorption is very rapid, stabilizing as saturation is reached.

Figure 7. Hydraulic mortar sample water absorption trends

Figure 8. Aerial mortar sample water absorption trends.

The salt crystallization test causes both the growth of efflorescence and accelerated mechanical stress, due to possible sub-efflorescence. The increase in weight in mortar was minimal; sometimes loss of materials and/or cracks occurred. The weight variations in all the samples are well visible in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Weight variation due to the salt crystallization test for: a) natural stone samples, b) hydraulic mortar samples, c) aerial mortar samples.

In the case of ghiara- and azolo-based mortars, results obtained highlight that the higher microporosity of the ghiara mortars is certainly responsible for their greater water absorption by capillarity (Fig. 10a) as well as for their lower resistance to salt crystallization (Fig. 10b) with respect to azolo-based ones.

Figure 10. a) Trend of water absorption by capillarity (a) and weight variation due to salt crystallization (b) in azolo mortar (CA) and ghiara mortar (CG).

Results will aim at understanding degradation mechanisms and developing preventive solutions for resilient cultural heritage. Moreover, they will support the development of mathematical models to describe geomaterial degradation under mechanical stress.

2.3 Metals

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2.3.1 State of the art

Sulfurization due to atmospheric hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and organic sulfur compounds is well known as the primary cause of tarnishing of silver objects. The most widespread prevention strategies used to protect silver cultural heritage from tarnishing involve the application of polymeric coatings. Acrylic resins and nitrocellulose lacquers are the most widely used, ensuring reversibility, low toxicity, chemical stability and preservation of the aesthetic features of the artefact [63]. The thickness of the coating layer is a crucial parameter to consider when analysing its protection effectiveness. Previous studies investigated the effects of artificial aging due to H₂S exposure of silver treated with different types of lacquer coatings [64,65], but did not explore, in detail, the relationships between thickness and protection effectiveness. This project aims to quantitatively determine how the thickness of a protective coating influences the tarnishing intensity of silver objects exposed to H₂S. Such a correlation is essential to a reliable comparison of the effectiveness of silver protectives and allows identifying the minimum film thickness required for optimal protection against silver tarnishing.

2.3.2 Key-parameters of degradation

Twelve sterling silver coupons were coated with two types of protective products: the acrylic Paraloid® B72 (supplied by CTS, Italy), and the nitrocellulose lacquer Zapon® (supplied by Lechler, Italy). Solutions with different concentrations were applied on the surfaces of the mock-ups as

described in deliverable 2.2 to get an uneven distribution of the polymeric film resulting in different thickness values. For each coupon, the mean thickness of the polymeric film was evaluated using a ponderal method. Besides, Eddy Current (EC) measurements were carried out in the central part of the mock-up (Table 2).

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Table 2. Coatings on silver coupons, with indication of the thickness estimated by EC measurements and the mean thickness calculated from the polymers mass.

N. coupon	Polymer	Concentration (w/w%)	EC thickness (μm)	Thickness calculated by polymer mass (μm)
Ag109	Paraloid B72	25	49.3 ± 2.9	69.6 ± 0.3
Ag110	Paraloid B72	15	24.8 ± 1.6	38.1 ± 0.3
Ag111	Paraloid B72	10	16.0 ± 0.7	23.5 ± 0.3
Ag112	Paraloid B72	7.5	10.1 ± 0.9	12.7 ± 0.2
Ag113	Paraloid B72	5	7.5 ± 0.8	10.2 ± 0.2
Ag114	Paraloid B72	2	/	2.2 ± 0.2
Ag115	Zapon	70	64.3 ± 0.9	57.9 ± 0.3
Ag116	Zapon	50	42.1 ± 1.0	44.8 ± 0.2
Ag117	Zapon	30	23.5 ± 1.7	26.5 ± 0.2
Ag118	Zapon	20	11.7 ± 0.7	15.2 ± 0.2
Ag119	Zapon	10	6.5 ± 0.6	7.6 ± 0.2
Ag120	Zapon	5	/	3.7 ± 0.2

More punctual information on the thickness distribution of the polymeric coating on the surface of each coupon was obtained by means of micro-XRF mapping (see deliverable 2.2). This approach allowed for the assessment of the uneven polymer distribution on the metal surface, which gives rise to the coffee-ring effect (thickening near the edges of the coupon's surface) on both the Paraloid- and Zapon-treated mock-ups.

Additionally, UV fluorescence images allowed for the assessment of polymer distribution on Zapon-treated mock-ups.

Three uncoated silver coupons were prepared to be used as control. Unsupported films of protectives were also prepared to check the color steadiness of the polymers upon exposure to H_2S .

Accelerated aging tests were conducted by exposing the mock-ups to H_2S vapor.

They consisted of 12 steps, each with a duration varying between 46 and 95 hours. The total duration of the experiment was approximately 38.6 days. The concentration was monitored with a long-operating continuous detector, logging the H₂S concentration every 5 minutes. The H₂S peak concentration was comprised between 3.0 and 11.0 ppm in different steps, while the mean concentration varied between 2.2 and 5.5 ppm. Total exposure calculated for the entire test was E_{tot} = 137.2 ppm·day.

The effects of aging were evaluated by visual observation, colorimetric measurements and imaging analysis (see deliverable 2.2 for details).

The overall colorimetric alteration of the coupons is expressed as

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{\Delta L^{*2} + \Delta a^{*2} + \Delta b^{*2}}$$

where ΔL^* , Δa^* , Δb^* represent the variation of the L*, a*, and b* parameters with respect to the non-aged specimen. For each coupon, the increase in ΔE^* values are correlated to the exposure E (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Color variation ΔE^* throughout the 12 experimental steps of accelerated aging for Paraloid B72 (left) and Zapon (right) specimens, with indication of the thickness measured with EC test.

The coupons with the thinnest protective layers (both Paraloid B72 and Zapon) experienced colorimetric changes detectable to the naked eye after the first step of accelerated aging ($E = 4.2 \text{ ppm}\cdot\text{day}$). Coupons with thicker coatings exhibited differing behaviour depending on the protective product. The protective efficacy of Paraloid B72 reached a plateau at thicknesses exceeding about $25 \mu\text{m}$, displaying no further remarkable increase of protection beyond this value. In contrast, coupons treated with Zapon demonstrated a progressive increase in the protection efficiency up to $60 \mu\text{m}$. Coupons of unsupported polymer films were not affected by any noticeable color alteration even at the highest exposure, confirming that the observed colorimetric changes are entirely attributable to the silver surface reaction with H_2S .

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The comparison between thickness maps obtained by $\mu\text{-XRF}$ scanning and VIS digital images revealed that tarnishing is controlled by the film thickness distribution on a micrometric scale (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Comparison between thickness mapping and digital image of Ag113 (up) and Ag119 (down) coupons at t12 exposure.

A comparison of the two products at similar film thicknesses demonstrated that Zapon was the more effective protective coating. Neither of the two products provided long-term protection at film thickness below approximately 25 μm , although it should be noted that exposures reached in the experiment are extremely high (simulating levels achievable over the course of many hundred years in indoor conditions).

The thickness of the polymer film is a key parameter in protecting silver objects from tarnishing. An outcome of this research is a strong recommendation to include the thickness distribution in the protocols to test protective efficacy.

2.4 Works on paper

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2.4.1 State of the art

On photographic paper, to date, only a few studies have considered the features and mechanisms of biological degradation of photographic artworks. Additionally, it is worth noting that until now, the few published works on photographic artworks have focused either solely on microbial characterization or solely on their chemical degradation, without simultaneously considering both aspects [66–71]. The present recent is the first characterization study of the microbial community and chemical degradation state of an artwork from the *Terrae Motus* modern art collection, thereby serving as a guide for subsequent research endeavors.

On paper, research was focused on the microbiological degradation of paper-based artifacts, with sampling conducted on books and documents selected

based on their conservation state and environmental conditions. Understanding and monitoring the growth mechanisms of biodeteriogens and their impact on paper are critical for developing effective conservation strategies. This necessitates methods capable of early detection and ongoing monitoring of microorganisms to assess their activity and the resulting effects on paper over time [72–74].

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2.4.2 Key-parameters of degradation

The study of photographic materials was performed by combining molecular sequencing methods (Sanger and HTS approach) and non-invasive vibrational spectroscopy to get new insights into the microbial communities thriving on photographic material and the chemical degradation of the print.

Regarding paper, a detailed study on biodeteriogens on paper identified fungi as the primary concern. Sampling were carried out in three libraries: the Biblioteca Capitolare in Benevento, the Biblioteca della Società dei Naturalisti in Naples, and the Biblioteca della Società Napoletana di Storia Patria, in Naples. Visible deterioration signs (e.g., stains and delamination) were sampled using sterile swabs, while air sampling—both passive and active—was performed in critical environments using Petri dishes with MALT and a microbiological air sampler. Temperature and humidity were recorded during all sessions. Fungal strains isolated from swabs were cultured on selective media (PDA, MALT, YES, CYA, CD) and identified through morphological (optical and fluorescence microscopy with Lactophenol blue and Calcofluor) and molecular methods, applying ITS, β -tubulin, and calmodulin markers. To evaluate cellulolytic activity, strains were tested on CMC agar with Congo Red staining, and proteolytic activity was

assessed using SMA and GEL agar; these tests are ongoing. Fungi were classified based on the damage they cause, and cellulase was selected as the target enzyme due to its significant role in paper degradation. Standard cellulase from *Trichoderma reesei* and specific antibodies were procured for preliminary tests to identify microorganisms on paper [74]. Further experimental details are described in deliverable 2.2.

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The degradation mechanism of photographic paper of the 20th century was object of study and published in *Heritage Science* [75]. Particularly we focused on photographs printed on silver gelatine. The underside multilayered verso page of the photograph covered by cellulose acetate was attacked by the microbiological contaminants, emphasizing a two-step mechanism associated with a different coloration of the verso page of the photograph (white/yellow/brown). These results established a link between microbial communities colonizing ancient photographic materials, paper decomposition, and the enzymatic patterns of the retrieved microorganisms. The yellow areas reasonably underwent to a reversible microbial attachment on the acetate coating, whereas in the brown area microbiological degradation reached the support paper.

The present work represents the first characterization study of the microbial community and chemical degradation state of an artwork from the Terrae Motus modern art collection at the Royal Palace of Caserta, thereby serving as a guide for subsequent research endeavors. The combined approach used in this study paves the way for a far-sighted non-invasive methodology to study modern non-conventional artworks, such as photographs.

Understanding the factors contributing to fungal infestation on cultural heritage artifacts and the consequent degradation is crucial for implementing effective mitigation strategies, considering the presence of organic residues, and environmental conditions promoting fungal proliferation. Additionally, environmental conditions, such as temperature and humidity fluctuations, may play a role in promoting fungal proliferation on vulnerable artifacts. The handling, exposure and storage conditions of artwork inhabited by human opportunistic pathogenic fungi should be evaluated with care, continuously monitored and, if necessary, improved. By understanding the implications of fungal infestations and implementing effective mitigation strategies, conservators can better safeguard these precious objects for future generations.

3. Predictive models for degradation

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3.1 State of the art

Photochemical degradation processes in paintings gained significant attention within the scientific community, as evidenced by various multidisciplinary contributions to this field [2,76]. In [45,77], mathematical models are built to capture the complex interplay of light radiation and environmental factors, providing comprehensive frameworks to investigate and predict deterioration processes. Here, we consider the light-induced conversion of a primary reactant, A , into a product compound, B . Let $c_A(z, t)$ and $c_B(z, t)$ denote the concentrations of the reactant A and the product B , respectively, at spatial position $z \in [0, L]$ and time $t \in [0, T]$. The evolution of concentrations is described by the following system

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial c_A}{\partial t}(z, t) = -K(c_A(z, t), c_B(z, t), w(z))c_A(z, t), \\ \frac{\partial c_B}{\partial t}(z, t) = K(c_A(z, t), c_B(z, t), w(z))c_A(z, t), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with $c_A(z, 0)$ and $c_B(z, 0)$ known initial concentrations and $w(z)$ represents the humidity level. The photocatalytic reaction rate $K(\cdot)$ incorporates the dynamic effects of several factors and non-linear integral operators are employed to capture the non-local effect of radiation. The dependence of the process on the system temperature and environmental conditions is expressed through Arrhenius' law [78] with the term

$$f(z) = \mathcal{A} \exp\left\{-\frac{E_a}{RT_K}\right\} w(z), \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{A} is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor, E_a is the activation energy of the reaction, R is the gas constant and $T_{\mathcal{K}}$ is the temperature. We further consider that the chemical process is triggered by light within a specific wavelength range $[\lambda_m, \lambda_M]$ which corresponds to photon energies sufficiently high to trigger the reaction. Therefore, according to the Beer-Lambert law [79], the light intensity is defined as follows

$$I\left(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta\right) = I_0(\lambda) \exp\left\{-\int_0^z \mu_a(\lambda, c_A(\zeta, t), c_B(\zeta, t)) d\zeta\right\}, \quad (3)$$

where, denoted by $\varepsilon_A(\lambda)$ and $\varepsilon_B(\lambda)$ the molar absorption coefficients for the reagent A and the product B , respectively, the system's absorbance μ_a reads

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_a(\lambda, c_A(\zeta, t), c_B(\zeta, t)) &= \varepsilon_A(\lambda)c_A(\zeta, t) + \varepsilon_B(\lambda)c_B(\zeta, t) \\ &= (\varepsilon_A(\lambda) - \varepsilon_B(\lambda))c_A(\zeta, t) + \varepsilon_B(\lambda)c_A(\zeta, t). \end{aligned}$$

Following the approach in [80–82] the overall light penetration effect is modeled as

$$\int_{\lambda_m}^{\lambda_M} \frac{2\hat{I}(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta)}{\hat{I}^2(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta) + 1} d\lambda, \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{I}(\cdot) = I(\cdot)/I_{ref}$ and I_{ref} is a given reference value.

The conservativity property of (1) ensures that, regardless of the form of $K(\cdot)$ the following linear invariant holds

$$c_A(z, t) + c_B(z, t) = c_A(z, 0) + c_B(z, 0), \quad \forall (z, t) \in [0, L] \times [0, T],$$

Which allows us to disregard the second equation of (1), under the assumption that no product is present at the onset of the reaction. From now on, for the sake of brevity, we adopt the notation $c(z, t)$ to refer to $c_A(z, t)$. Accounting for the system (1) and the contributions in (2)-(4), we drew up the model

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial c}{\partial t}(z, t) = f(z)c(z, t) \int_{\lambda_m}^{\lambda_M} \frac{2\hat{I}(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta)}{\hat{I}^2(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta) + 1} d\lambda, \\ I\left(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, t) d\zeta\right) = I_0(\lambda) \exp\left\{-\varepsilon_\delta(\lambda) \int_0^z c(\zeta, t) d\zeta - \varepsilon_B(\lambda)C_0(z)\right\}, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

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where $\varepsilon_\delta(\lambda) = \varepsilon_A(\lambda) - \varepsilon_B(\lambda)$ and $C_0(z) = \int_0^z c(\zeta, 0) d\zeta > 0$ are known functions. We refer to [77] for theoretical insights on the existence of a unique model's solution.

3.2 Numerical Simulation Method

The function $c(z, t)$ represents the concentration of a chemical reactant undergoing degradation and is therefore required to be positive and monotonically non-increasing over time. However, the development of numerical methods, that are both of high order and unconditionally preserve these properties, poses significant challenges. To this end, we address and discretize the implicit Volterra integral equation

$$c(z, t) = \exp\left\{-f(z) \int_0^t \int_{\lambda_m}^{\lambda_M} \frac{2\hat{I}(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, \tau) d\zeta)}{\hat{I}^2(\lambda, \int_0^z c_A(\zeta, \tau) d\zeta) + 1} d\lambda d\tau\right\}, \quad (6)$$

that is equivalent to the first equation in (5) and is derived from it through integration with respect to time, considering the properties of the continuous solution.

Let $\Delta z, \Delta t, \Delta \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$ denote the spatial, temporal and frequency stepsizes, respectively. Define N_z, N_t and N_λ as positive integers such that $L = N_z \Delta z$, $T = N_t \Delta t$ and $\lambda_M = \lambda_m + N_\lambda \Delta \lambda$. Consider the uniform meshes $z_j = j \Delta z$, for $j = 0, \dots, N_z$, $t_n = n \Delta t$, for $n = 0, \dots, N_t$ and $\lambda_l = \lambda_m + l \Delta \lambda$, for $l = 0, \dots, N_\lambda$. To simulate model (5)-(6) we propose the fully-explicit numerical

method

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_n^{j,l} = I(\lambda_l) \exp \left\{ -\mu \left(\varepsilon_\delta(\lambda_l) \Delta z \sum_{r=0}^{j-1} c_n^r + \varepsilon_B(\lambda_l) C_0(z_j) \right) \right\}, \\ p_{n+1}^j = c_n^j \exp \left\{ -\Delta t \Delta \lambda f(z_j) \sum_{l=0}^{N_\lambda-1} F(\alpha_n^{j,l}) \right\}, \\ \beta_n^{j,l} = I(\lambda_l) \exp \left\{ -\mu \left(\varepsilon_\delta(\lambda_l) \frac{\Delta z}{2} (c_n^0 + 2 \sum_{r=1}^{j-1} c_n^r + c_n^j) + \varepsilon_B(\lambda_l) C_0(z_j) \right) \right\}, \\ \beta_{n+1}^{j,l} = I(\lambda_l) \exp \left\{ -\mu \left(\varepsilon_\delta(\lambda_l) \frac{\Delta z}{2} (p_{n+1}^0 + 2 \sum_{r=1}^{j-1} p_{n+1}^r + p_{n+1}^j) + \varepsilon_B(\lambda_l) C_0(z_j) \right) \right\}, \\ \gamma_{n+1}^j = F(\beta_n^{j,0}) + F(\beta_{n+1}^{j,0}) + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{N_\lambda-1} \left(F(\beta_n^{j,l}) + F(\beta_{n+1}^{j,l}) \right) + F(\beta_n^{j,N_\lambda}) + F(\beta_{n+1}^{j,N_\lambda}), \\ c_{n+1}^j = c_n^j \exp \left\{ -\frac{\Delta t \Delta \lambda}{2} f(z_j) \gamma_{n+1}^j \right\}, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

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where $c_n^j \approx c(z_j, t_n)$ is the approximated solution and $F: x \in \mathbb{R}_0^+ \rightarrow 2x/(x^2 + 1) \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$. The scheme (7) is quadratically convergent and yields positive numerical solutions with no restrictions on the spatial, temporal and frequency step sizes (detailed proofs of such results are provided in [45,77]).

3.3 Cadmium pigments degradation modeling and simulation

The integro-differential model (5) is suitable to describe the deterioration mechanisms of cadmium sulfide-based paintings.

When exposed to light and high moisture, cadmium yellow, primarily composed of cadmium sulfide (CdS), undergoes a photocatalytic reaction that produces cadmium sulfate ($CdSO_4$) and results in color degradation (cf. Section 2, par. 2.1.2.2). The overall process, described in [17] as follows:

is initiated by supra-band-gap light with photon energy greater than 2.42 eV, and therefore by light within a spectral range corresponding to wavelengths shorter than $\lambda_M = 512.331$ nm.

To simulate the light-induced cadmium yellows degradation process, we consider the model (5) with the parameters specified in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameters of the simulation

Params.	Descriptions	Units	Values
c^0	Initial CdS concentration	mol cm ⁻³	$3.34 \cdot 10^{-21}$
L	Depth of painted layer	cm	$7.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$
T	Reference time	s	$2.30 \cdot 10^6$
λ_m	Minimum wavelength	nm	$3.80 \cdot 10^2$
λ_M	Band-gap wavelength	nm	$5.12 \cdot 10^2$
\mathcal{A}	Arrhenius pre-exponential factor	cm ² mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$1.00 \cdot 10^8$
E_a	Activation energy	J mol ⁻¹	$7.78 \cdot 10^{-19}$
R	Gas constant	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$8.31 \cdot 10^0$
T_K	Temperature	K	$2.98 \cdot 10^2$
w^r	Humidity reference value	mol cm ⁻³	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-6}$
w_b	Humidity lower threshold	mol cm ⁻³	$5.77 \cdot 10^{-7}$
I_{ref}	Irradiance reference value	W ² m ⁻² nm ⁻¹	$3.48 \cdot 10^0$

The illumination function $I(\lambda)$, shown in Figure 13 is derived by a local quadratic regression of the emission data for the UV-filtered xenon lamp reported in [83]. The molar absorptivity $\varepsilon_c(\lambda)$ of cadmium sulfide is obtained from the *hex - CdS* diffuse reflectance UV-VIS spectra in [17]. Specifically, given the reflectance $R(\lambda)$ at a relative humidity level of 95% we assume a zero transmittance and, following the arguments in [84], we compute $\varepsilon_c(\lambda) = -\log(R(\lambda)) / (c^0 L_c)$, where $L_c = 10^{-4}$ cm represents the thickness of the cadmium sulfate top crust. As for the *CdSO₄*, in absence of experimental data, we assume a proportionality between the two molar absorptivities and take $\varepsilon_g(\lambda) = 4\varepsilon_c(\lambda)$. Furthermore, the environmental humidity required to trigger the reaction is modeled by the following water profile $w(z) = (w^r - w_h)(L - z)$ which decreases linearly with depth.

Figure 13. Absolute irradiance and molar absorptivities.

Figure 14 illustrates the outcomes of the simulation with the scheme (7) and $\Delta z = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{cm}$, $\Delta t = 0.32 \text{ h}$, $\Delta \lambda = 6.60 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{nm}$. In compliance with experimental observations, the degradation phenomenon is predominantly confined to a shallow region of the painting due to the formation of a CdSO_4 reflective layer which significantly attenuates light penetration. Further simulations under different experimental conditions are discussed in [45], where a detailed local sensitivity analysis of the dimensionless model is also conducted. The analysis demonstrates that model (5) exhibits limited sensitivity to parameter perturbations.

Figure 14. Space-time evolution, near the surface, of CdS concentration.

The emergence of an S-shaped pattern in Figure 14 highlights the formation of cadmium sulfate on the surface and its gradual penetration deeper into the layers. A passivation effect induced by the $CdSO_4$ is evident as well. Indeed, higher concentrations of cadmium sulfate, which is white and highly reflective, visibly retard the overall reaction process.

To quantify the passivation effect, given a threshold value ψ , we analyze the behavior of the dimensionless separation front

$$\Sigma_\psi(t) = \min\{\zeta \in [0, L]: c(\zeta, t) \geq c^0 \cdot \psi\},$$

that represents the spatial point from which, at time t , the $CdSO_4$ concentration goes below the threshold $c^0 \cdot (1 - \psi)$. Figure 15 illustrates the front approximated values $\Sigma_\psi^n \approx \Sigma_\psi(t_n)$ derived from the numerical solution computed by (7) when $\psi \in \{0.7, 0.8, 0.9\}$. These plots indicate that the separation front

Figure 15. Separation front evolution with respect to the logarithm of time

indicate that the separation front

progresses linearly respectively to the logarithm of time, whatever the value of

ψ . We remark that $\partial_t^2 \Sigma_\psi(t) \propto -\frac{1}{t^2}$ represents an estimate, as time goes by, of the reaction speed reduction due to passivation.

The optimization of the proposed model is ongoing via the exploitation of experimental data recorded from the monitoring of the photoaging of cadmium yellow paint mock-ups as described in Section 2 (par. 2.1.2.2).

4. Conclusions

This deliverable has identified key degradation parameters for selected cultural heritage materials (pigments, organic binders, stone, metals, and paper) and developed a predictive model for the photodegradation of cadmium yellow pigments.

Several factors contribute to the degradation of certain pigment classes (copper-, sulfide-, lead-, and cobalt-based) in paint materials. These include specific types of white light, particular relative humidity and temperature ranges, and exposure to various saline solutions. Research on the impact of pigment chemistry on the degradation of proteinaceous binders, such as the deamidation process, suggests that the pigment type does not significantly influence the extent of deamidation.

With respect to stone materials, both chemical composition and porosity are identified as key factors influencing water absorption characteristics and the propensity for salt crystallization.

In the conservation of metallic artifacts, specifically silver, comparative analysis of Paraloid B72 and Zapon as protective coatings established the importance of polymer film thickness in mitigating tarnish. Zapon exhibited superior performance in these tests.

In the case of paper-based materials, research has established a correlation between the microbial communities colonizing historical photographic materials, the degradation of the paper substrate, and the patterns of the retrieved microorganisms. Furthermore, fluctuations in temperature and relative humidity are recognized as key environmental drivers that can promote

fungal proliferation on these vulnerable artifacts.

The datasets and mock-ups produced in Work Package 2 are now available to optimize the existing mathematical predictive degradation models and to further the activities of Spoke 5, Work Package 1, *“Advanced Non-Invasive Methods for Sustainable Diagnostics in Heritage Science”*. These resources are particularly relevant to the development of 2D/3D imaging scanners.

Selected datasets will also be contributed to open-access databases for the Heritage Science community, developed within the PNNR H2IOSC project, the *“Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud”*, specifically the *“Scientific Digital Hub For Painting Collections”* (WP7, Task 6.7).

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